

Forecasting flexibility of charging of electric vehicles: Tree and cluster-based methods

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ABSTRACT

Scheduling electric vehicle charging sessions allows to aggregate flexibility in order to minimize energy costs and reduce congestion in the electricity grid. Existing research shows that user input for energy and parking duration does not serve as a reliable prediction. The study presents an evaluation of the forecast error and computational performance of the different models. Two main methods are investigated: tree-based (gradient boosted trees LightGBM) and cluster-based (Gaussian mixture model). We also present a novel dynamic cluster-based method, the Similar Sessions method, which employs the similarity between charging sessions based on numerical variables. The results highlight the importance of selecting the forecast model influenced by the availability of training data. The effect of user registration on the accuracy of the forecast is investigated. The tests are run using *ACN-Data* dataset of Electric Vehicle charging sessions in California, United States. While underperforming on a small dataset with a short look-back period, tree-based methods show superiority while the charging data are accumulating. The Similar Sessions method shows superior accuracy under various data availability conditions. The proposed method requires no prior training, but has slower computational performance in deployment.

1. Introduction

Global transport sector relies strongly on fossil fuels and is estimated to be responsible for nearly 37% of CO₂ emissions. This number includes a majority contribution from road transport, which continues to be largely relying (97%) on oil products [1]. The electrification of road vehicles is recognized by governments as a promising pathway to reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The car market echoes this ambition, as electric cars made up almost 10% of global car sales in 2021 and continued to grow in 2022 [2]. The rapid expansion of electric vehicle (EV) fleets is accompanied by a corresponding increase in investments in public charging infrastructure. Most cars remain stationary for extended periods; therefore, electric vehicle batteries and associated charging units often remain idle. The resulting discrepancy between the minimal necessary and actual duration of charging sessions creates flexibility, which can be valuable both in energy market arbitrage and in providing services aimed at balancing the electricity grid. EV batteries, managed in sufficiently large aggregations, can provide power flexibility to participate in ancillary service markets, for example, frequency restoration. Such services are referred to in literature as “regulation” or “secondary regulation” [3].

1.1. Problem statement

The flexibility in timing and power allocation for EV charging offers the possibility of optimal scheduling with cost-effectiveness and consideration for grid limitations. This optimization approach is commonly known as ‘smart charging’, which employs algorithms based on specific charging session parameters like total energy demand and duration. By utilizing user identification, arrival time details, and historical charging session data, these parameters can potentially be forecasted for individual EV arrivals. We set the objective for the forecasting model to learn functions for estimating duration $\delta^{(j)}$ and energy $\epsilon^{(j)}$ of individual charging session i of a known user j

$$\hat{\delta}^{(i,j)} = f_{\text{duration}}(a_i, j)$$

$$\hat{\epsilon}^{(i,j)} = f_{\text{energy}}(a_i, j)$$

Both functions are trained on a dataset \mathcal{D} consisting of historical charging sessions, where $\mathcal{D} = \{\mathbf{s}\}_{i=1}^N = \{(a_i, j, \delta^{(i,j)}, \epsilon^{(i,j)})\}_{i=1}^N$.

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1.2. Contribution and structure of the paper

In this paper, we aim to contribute to the topic of forecasting the behavior of EV users by examining the crucial issue of selecting an appropriate forecasting model based on the availability of training data.

1. We revisit the dataset presented in [4] and contribute more analysis of the data intensiveness of cluster-based (GMM) and tree-based (LGBM) state-of-the-art models.
2. We demonstrate the relation between the forecasting model selection and the availability of training data, and present a detailed study of the effect of user identification data on forecast accuracy.
3. As part of our contributions, a novel ‘‘Similar Sessions’’ (SimS) approach is proposed, which estimates the charging duration and the energy demand of an electric vehicle by computing similarity algorithms on the historical data of charging sessions. The effectiveness of the SimS approach is showcased through its competence in terms of forecast accuracy and computational performance.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we provide an overview of the literature on existing methods for forecasting EV charging behavior. In Section 3, we describe the dataset, analyze the statistical properties of the data, and explain the train–test partition. Section 4 outlines the evaluated forecasting methods, their core principles, and the evaluation methodology. The section includes the description for our proposed ‘Similar Sessions’ approach, including its implementation. In Section 5, the results for the accuracy evaluation on a test set are presented and discussed. Finally, in Section 6, we present our conclusions and suggestions on the directions for future research.

2. Literature review

There is a growing body of research on modeling the electric load of electric vehicles charging. Firstly, we review the articles that present methods for forecasting the EV charging time-series directly using models trained on historical data. This approach characterizes the forecasting of the load in controllable assets and is illustrated schematically in Fig. 1(a).

Article [5] proposes an aggregate EV charging demand forecasting method based on the auto-regressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) model to predict charging demand for electric vehicles. Uncertainty in charging behavior is addressed by solving a chance-constrained scheduling problem using the aggregate forecast as input.

EV charging data commonly shows patterns in user behavior, which can be captured efficiently by clustering methods. Using data from individual meters at charging stations, the authors of the article [6] identify five types of batteries defined by energy and power capacities, and four main clusters of charging habits. This information is used to generate probabilistic forecasts of the aggregated load, as well as day-ahead consumption scenarios for a single EV and the aggregated fleet. The proposed approach is found to be more efficient than the naive and gradient-boosting benchmark models. The improvement is notable in modeling the lower tail of the distribution. [7] presents a global method that employs a combination of a clustered multi-node learning (CMNL) and Gaussian processes (GP). The CMNL component considers the group structures among different nodes (stations) and relies more on the nodes that are in the same cluster. The GP component is specific to each individual station and captures random fluctuations or unique characteristics within the station’s load data. The method is validated on the real-world dataset in Utah, USA and outperforms the benchmark models, including linear regression, ARIMA, SVM and Feed-Forward Neural Networks. When estimating the individual load at the charging stations, the authors make the assumption that EVs are charged uniformly.

The increasing popularity of machine learning methods has found many applications in research on forecasting EV charging loads. Van Kriekinge et al. [8] study long short-term memory network (LSTM) configurations with a dynamic learning rate to forecast the day-ahead charging demand of electric vehicles with a 15-minute time resolution. The added benefit of exogenous weather variables is also shown. In [9], multiple models were evaluated for one-step ahead load prediction at city aggregation and charger level using two years of EV charging load from the Korean Ministry of Environment. The data is aggregated into total load times series per charging station, city and country. The study finds that multivariate models such as ARIMA, ANN, and LSTM show higher accuracy than univariate models. The TBATS model is useful when only univariate values are available, and the LSTM model performs best at the individual charger level. The authors also analyze the data intensiveness of different models, i.e., the sensitivity of the forecast prediction to the length of a historical set. When fitting the models with historical sets of varying lengths, i.e. 3/6/18 months, it was observed that the length of the training set was less influential in the short-term forecast, while the longer data notably improves the model performance in mid- to long-term forecast. More historical data generally upgrade the forecasting power while facilitating the long-term robustness of a model.

An optimally scheduled charging process for electric vehicles (EVs), often referred to as smart charging, makes use of the flexibility of time and power of the charging of the vehicles. Unlike non-controllable load assets, an EV charger can adjust the power and time to match the needs of the grid and the user. Making electric vehicle chargers fully controllable changes the traditional view on load forecasting. The differences between approaches are demonstrated in Fig. 1. The principal difference between the underlying forecasting approaches is the limited predictive power of historical load data. With a non-controllable load asset, shown in 1(a), the historical load time-series is indicative of the future load. Instead, when an EV charger is fully controllable, as shown in 1(b), the real-time arrivals, parameters of charging sessions and an optimized schedule of control signals are more indicative of the charger’s future load profile.

Individual charging session parameters, such as user arrival times, as well as energy demands and parking duration, are essential parameters for scheduling optimization and estimating the potential flexibility resource. The effective aggregate demand for an EV charging pool can be simulated by adding the charging profiles of individual charging sessions, subject to scheduling optimization.

Decoupling the modeling of user arrivals and charging session specifications, as shown in 1(b), is advantageous in scale-up studies when the known user behavior is interpolated for an anticipated increase in EV drivers. In some pilot sites [4,10], it is a well-established practice to collect user-specified session requirements directly from the user. These preferences can be taken as parameters to optimize the operation of the electric vehicle charger. However, as noted in Lee et al. [4], users lack the incentive to provide accurate predictions for their parking duration and energy demands. Data-driven forecasting methods can be used to improve the accuracy of the predictions.

We review the publications that discuss forecasting the EV charging session parameters. There is a wide range of methods for predicting the behavior of EV users. For a comprehensive review, we recommend referring to [11]. On this account, select aspects relevant to the discussion and the subject of this research are discussed.

Some researchers take estimates of departure time and energy demands as declared by users [12]. The paper [4] presents ACN-Data, a dynamic dataset of workplace EV charging with more than 2 years of data and more than 30,000 sessions at two sites, Caltech and the JPL campus. The paper uses the data and presents a method utilizing Gaussian mixture models (GMMs) to predict the charging duration and energy delivered to drivers. The authors explore two model approaches, a population-level GMM (P-GMM) based on the overall training data,

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram explaining the difference in modeling approaches used in estimation of aggregate EV charging load profiles.

and individual-level GMMs (I-GMMs) trained for each user by fine-tuning the weights of the components of the P-GMM with sessions linked to a specific user. The derived approaches significantly beat the estimates provided by EV users directly, making the case that data-driven models are a more reliable prediction for these parameters. The authors include an analysis of the prediction accuracy with different sizes of training data. The authors demonstrate a trade-off between prediction quality and data size, with the best performance found using a 30-day training set on a Caltech site. The authors also show that the parameters declared by the driver are not reliable predictions of the session duration and charged energy. This can be attributed to two factors. First, there is an incentive misalignment, as users are more interested in getting the most energy in the shortest amount of time than providing the most accurate prediction, unless there is an additional financial gain in place. Second, there may be a lack of awareness about the car battery specifications, such as the battery capacity or the vehicle's consumption per mile.

Huber et al. [13] develops a forecasting method using German data of travel logs from 6465 car users. The aim is to generate probabilistic forecasts of the duration of parking and the energy requirements. The study employs various machine learning algorithms, including quantile regression, multi-layer perceptrons with tilted loss function, and multivariate conditional kernel density estimators. The results show that the use of probabilistic forecasts is shown to lead to more efficient scheduling compared to point forecasts, resulting in fewer interruptions and increased driver mobility.

Among many publications showing applications of machine learning to predict EV user behavior, the decision tree methods often demonstrate the best performing models. Applied to the charging behavior of electric vehicles, tree-based methods are found in several implementations, including Random Forest [14] and Gradient-boosted Decision Tree (GBDT) implementations, such as XGBoost [15] or LightGBM [16]. The dominance of tree-based methods has also been prominent in other applications dealing with tabular data. The GBDT algorithm is reported [17] to get top places in most of forecasting competitions on Kaggle, a popular online platform for data scientists and machine learning practitioners. GBDT is found to be particularly effective in modeling external information, dealing with in-sample level shifts, and cross-learning information from similar series. GBDT shows superior performance both in estimating point predictions and in modeling uncertainty [18,19]. The resilience to adaptation of tree-based methods is often attributed to the inability to extrapolate trends (without appropriate preprocessing), as well as poor performance of the method

for small datasets. The relationship between the type of forecasting algorithm and the size of the data is investigated in the following article.

3. Dataset

For the purpose of this research we use an open-source *ACN-Data* dataset [4], a collection of data on workplace charging sessions, including individual session parameters, as well as the respective time series of the power output at charger. The dataset contains information of the arrival and departure times of electric vehicles, the requested energy, and the actual energy delivered. The dataset was collected from 55 charging stations in a parking garage at Caltech campus. The parking site is open to public, commonly used by Caltech employees as well as visitors of a gym, located nearby. As a result, the data collected at the Caltech site provides a representative sample of charging usage in a mixed environment, catering to both workplace and public charging needs. A log of 4957 charging sessions in the duration of 652 days between March 11, 2018 and January 1, 2022 is used in the model training and evaluation process.

3.1. Preprocessing

Preprocessing and feature creation steps were performed to prepare the input features for use in forecasting models. The first step was to calculate the parking duration for each session taking the difference between the disconnect time and the connection time. In order to maintain real-world representation and preserve the authenticity of charging behaviors, no specific preprocessing with respect to the outliers has been conducted. This approach enhances model generalization, allowing for better handling of unforeseen scenarios.

To capture the cyclical nature of the timestamp variable, new features were created for hour, month, and weekday. For each set of features, two new variables were created using the sine and cosine functions of the timestamp. This was done to account for the cyclical nature of time variables and avoid the problem of treating them as linear variables. To identify holidays, a list of US holidays was obtained and used to create a new binary feature, which indicates whether a given record occurred on a holiday. Similarly, a binary feature was

Table 1
Date intervals of data partitions for training and test data.

Number of days	Starting date	Ending date	Number of sessions
30 (test)	01-Dec-2019	01-Jan-2020	157
30	01-Nov-2019	31-Nov-2019	196
60	02-Oct-2019	31-Nov-2019	403
120	03-Aug-2019	31-Nov-2019	910
240	05-Apr-2019	31-Nov-2019	2127
360	06-Dec-2018	31-Nov-2019	3627
480	08-Aug-2018	31-Nov-2019	4779

created to indicate whether a given record occurred on a weekend day. The final list of model variables is as follows.

- Categorical features:
 - $userID$
- Numerical Features:
 - $hour_x$ – $month_x$ – $weekday_x$
 - $hour_y$ – $month_y$ – $weekday_y$

3.2. Train–test split

We revisit the experimental setup as reported in [4], specifically the definitions of the test set including users \mathcal{U} with more than 20 sessions. The size of the training set remains to be 30 days in January. However, we add one more year to the potential size of the training data. Therefore, the test set lies in the period between December 1, 2019 and January 1, 2020. A range of intervals with different look-back periods from 30 to 480 days used as test and training data is shown in Table 1. Note that the number of sessions within each partition is not strictly proportional to the duration of the time period. The data contains more claimed sessions in the summer period. The time intervals are shown at the bottom of Fig. 2. The test set is marked in a darker color.

3.3. Analysis

We select the energy delivery and the duration of charging sessions as target variables. The respective series are shown in Fig. 2. The plots indicate that the time-series data do not show any significant trend or seasonal patterns, suggesting that they are stationary. However, there are some noticeable outliers in the data in both the energy delivery and parking duration data.

In Fig. 3, the distributions of the session parameters are shown for an expanding look-back period in a so-called ‘ridge’ plot. The plot demonstrates the evolution of the variables’ distributions with the increasing volume of historical data. As the look-back period increases, the numerical distribution of the variables tends to regress towards more pronounced peaks within a mixed Gaussian distribution. This phenomenon may also potentially arise from yearly seasonality patterns, yet the examination of the time-series plot in Fig. 2 fails to reveal any indications of seasonality in the data.

Fig. 4 presents four box plots showing the distributions of energy delivery and parking duration of charging sessions grouped by the hour of arrival of the vehicle, distinguishing between weekdays and weekends. The results demonstrate a discernible daily seasonality, particularly during the weekdays, where morning arrivals typically stay connected within the same day, while evening arrivals exhibit a greater variance in parking time. Similar patterns are also observed in energy delivery data, with vehicles arriving in the evening being supplied with more energy on average. However, the distributions for weekends appear more compact, possibly due to a limitation in dataset — comprising only sessions from workplace charging. The clear differentiation between weekdays and weekends suggests a weekly seasonality.

4. Method

Based on the arrival time and user identification, we make predictions of waiting time and energy demands of the electric vehicle. Cluster-based Gaussian mixture model and a tree-based light gradient-boosted machine (LGBM) model are tested and compared for different look-back periods, indicative of data size. The Gaussian mixture model (GMM) is selected as a state-of-the-art model for predicting EV charging behavior as the benchmark model for the selected ACN dataset. The authors of the ACN-Data paper, which introduced the dataset used in the study, proposed it as an optimal method for predicting charging duration and energy delivered to drivers. On the other hand, LightGBM (LGBM) is chosen as a state-of-the-art model due to its proven track record in dominating competitions involving tabular data, as seen in the publications reviewed in Section 2. Furthermore, two simple methods are used as benchmarks, namely the input requests for charging energy and duration provided by the users themselves (“User Input”) and an estimate made using an average of historical charging sessions per user (“Hist. Mean per user”). The source code for downloading the data and running the models can be found in the github repository at [20]

4.1. Gaussian mixture models

Gaussian mixture models are used to model the behavior of EV drivers based on their charging patterns. The complete description of the method is provided in [4]. The data is represented by a set of vectors $\mathbf{s}_i = (a_i, \delta_i, \epsilon_i)$ with three values: arrival time a_i , duration δ_i , and total energy delivered ϵ_i . The GMM approach is model-driven, built on the assumptions that the data points are generated from a finite number of typical profiles, and the noise is Gaussian, which allows the model to cluster data points based on their profiles. The GMM is fit by estimating the parameters $\theta = (\pi_k, \mu_k, \Sigma_k)_{k=1}^K$ where π_k is a probability that the EV user has the profile k , μ_k is a means vector of a Gaussian random variable, and Σ_k is a covariance matrix. The probability density of observing a data point \mathbf{s} can then be approximated using the GMM. Assuming that the arrival time $a(j)$ of user j is known a priori, the model can predict the duration $\delta(j)$ and energy $\epsilon(j)$ to be delivered by user j as conditional Gaussians. These predictions are made using formulas that depend on the estimated parameters $\theta(j) = (\pi(j), \mu(j), \Sigma(j))_K$ for the user j , where $\mu(j)$ is a vector that contains the estimated arrival time, duration, and energy for the user j .

$$\delta^{(j)} = \sum_{k=1}^K \bar{\pi}_k^{(j)} \left(d_k^{(j)} + \left(\alpha^{(j)} - a_k^{(j)} \right) \frac{\Sigma_k^{(j)}(1, 2)}{\Sigma_k^{(j)}(1, 1)} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon^{(j)} = \sum_{k=1}^K \bar{\pi}_k^{(j)} \left(e_k^{(j)} + \left(\alpha^{(j)} - a_k^{(j)} \right) \frac{\Sigma_k^{(j)}(1, 3)}{\Sigma_k^{(j)}(1, 1)} \right) \quad (2)$$

where $\Sigma_k^{(j)}(1, 1)$, $\Sigma_k^{(j)}(1, 2)$ and $\Sigma_k^{(j)}(1, 3)$ are the first, second, and third entries of the covariance matrix. $\bar{\pi}_k^{(j)}$ are the modified weights conditioned on arrival time.

$$\bar{\pi}_k := \frac{p\left(\alpha^{(j)} \mid a_k^{(j)}, \Sigma_k^{(j)}(1, 1)\right)}{\sum_{k=1}^K p\left(\alpha^{(j)} \mid a_k^{(j)}, \Sigma_k^{(j)}(1, 1)\right)} \quad (3)$$

Two training approaches are tested for GMMs: population and individual level. On the individual level, the model is tuned on the data set of sessions with the same user.

4.2. Gradient boosted trees

Light Gradient Boosted Machine (LGBM) is a high performance gradient boosting framework that uses tree-based learning algorithms. LGBM is a single-output regression model. Therefore, the task is formulated for two separate regression problems, where the target variable is the charging duration δ or the energy demand ϵ . We examine the model algorithm following an example for the charging duration.

Fig. 2. Time-Series of training and test partitions for Caltech dataset.

Fig. 3. Ridge plots show numeric distributions across different look-back periods.

The learning process in LGBM involves iteratively growing decision trees and optimizing their splits to minimize the regression loss between the predicted charging duration $\hat{\delta}_i$ and the actual charging duration δ_i . The model learns to minimize the regression loss between the predicted and actual charging duration and energy demand. The objective function in LightGBM combines the regression loss function with regularization terms to control overfitting. The objective function is defined as follows:

$$\text{Objective} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N L(\delta_i, \hat{\delta}_i) + \lambda_1 \cdot \text{Regularization}_1 + \lambda_2 \cdot \text{Regularization}_2 \quad (4)$$

where:

- δ_i is the actual charging duration for the i th charging session,
- $\hat{\delta}_i$ is the predicted charging duration for the i th session,
- N is the total number of charging sessions in the training dataset,
- L is the regression loss function, set to mean absolute error (MAE),
- λ_1 and λ_2 are regularization parameters,

Regularization₁ and Regularization₂ are specific regularization terms, like L1 regularization (Lasso) and L2 regularization (Ridge).

The LGBM model, being a gradient boosting framework, builds multiple decision trees sequentially, where each new tree is trained to correct the errors of the previously trained trees. The final prediction for the charging duration $\hat{\delta}_i$ is the sum of predictions from all the individual trees. LGBM configurations includes a number of hyperparameters. An optimal combination of hyperparameters is searched using the Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) algorithm, implemented in optuna library [21]. The predefined ranges of hyperparameters that define the search space are given in the Table 2.

Table 2
Hyperparameters of LGBM.

Hyperparameter	Description	Range
num_leaves	Maximum number of leaves in one tree	[2, 200]
max_depth	Maximum depth of tree	[2, 5]
learning_rate	Learning rate	[0.001, 0.1]
min_data	Minimum number of data in one leaf	[1, 100]
lambda_l1	L1 regularization	[0.001, 1000]
lambda_l2	L2 regularization	[0.001, 1000]

LGBM is designed to be efficient and scalable for large datasets and can handle sparse data. In contrast to traditional gradient boosted algorithms that grow trees depth-wise, LGBM grows trees leaf-wise, which reduces the number of instances traversed during tree building and improves training efficiency. Additionally, LGBM supports categorical features, which can be converted into numerical features using one-hot encoding.

Some additional feature engineering is performed. The complete sequence of steps in preprocessing and modeling is shown in the diagram in Fig. 5. The training is run independently for each of the target variables. During the initial data exploration of Fig. 2, we found that the time series for parking duration exhibits signs of non-stationarities in data distribution. The variance of the data is not constant over time. To address this issue, we perform a log transformation on the parking duration target variable, a measure widely used in time-series analysis. Taking the natural logarithm compresses the range of values while reducing the influence of extreme values.

Fig. 4. Box plots depicting the distribution of energy delivery and parking duration of EV charging sessions by hour of arrival. Box plots summarize the distribution of data by displaying the median and quantile ranges. Outliers are dismissed for clarity.

Fig. 5. Workflow and dataflow diagram.

4.3. Similar sessions

In load forecasting, the similar day method has long been a reliable technique for predicting energy consumption. By analogy, we propose a novel method, called the similar session method (SimS), to address the challenge of predicting the charging behavior of EV users. However, similarity-based methods deal with a common challenge in identifying similarity patterns. The proposed approach draws inspiration from collaborative filtering, a technique commonly used in movie recommendation systems. Although clustering techniques are often used for this purpose, they come with certain limitations, such as need for model selection, hyperparameter search, and treatment of categorical variables.

To overcome these issues, we propose measuring similarity between vectors of session parameters, including calendar features of hour,

month, and year, as well as a dummy variable for the user identifier. Let s_{N+1} be the numerical vector representing the target charging session and s_i be the vector of a charging session from the historical dataset $D = \{s\}_{i=1}^N$. The pairwise similarity between two charging sessions is calculated in terms of a cosine similarity C :

$$C(s_{N+1}, s_i) = \cos(s_{N+1}, s_i) = \frac{s_{N+1} \cdot s_i}{\|s_{N+1}\| \|s_i\|} \quad (5)$$

where $\|s_{N+1}\|$ and $\|s_i\|$ denote the Euclidean norms of vectors s_{N+1} and s_i , respectively.

Let $C = C_1, C_2, \dots, C_N$ be the vector of similarity scores of all historical sessions. Then, the m most similar sessions to the target charging session s_{N+1} can be obtained by selecting the m indices corresponding to the highest values in the vector C . The set of these most similar sessions is denoted as $S_{\text{similar}} = s_{N+1}^{(1)}, s_{N+1}^{(2)}, \dots, s_{N+1}^{(m)}$.

Now, we can use this set S_{similar} to predict the charging duration δ^{N+1} and energy demand ϵ^{N+1} for the target charging session s_{N+1} . Let $\delta^{(i)}$ and $\epsilon^{(i)}$ represent the charging duration and energy demand of the i th session in S_{similar} . Then, the predicted charging duration $\hat{\delta}^{N+1}$ and the energy demand $\hat{\epsilon}^{N+1}$ for the target session s_{N+1} can be expressed as:

$$\hat{\delta}^{N+1} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \delta^{(i)} \quad (6)$$

$$\hat{\epsilon}^{N+1} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \epsilon^{(i)} \quad (7)$$

By averaging the respective parameters of the most similar sessions, we leverage the historical data to estimate the charging duration and energy demand for the target session s_{N+1} . This approach helps mitigate the impact of individual outliers and improves the accuracy of our predictions. The similar session method takes advantage of the patterns observed in sessions of both the same user and other users with matching arrival times. The design of the method entails one hyperparameter that denotes the number of similar sessions m used for calculations.

This approach is expected to be particularly efficient in the context of modeling the behavior of EV users. The method is meant to be very efficient in terms of data intensiveness. Compared to smart-meter data, charging session data is typically sparse and scattered over time. Therefore, such limitation in data quantity enables the calculation of the cosine distance to take an adequate amount of computation time and memory.

4.4. Evaluation method

Performance of four models, LGBM, P-GMM, I-GMM, and SimS, is evaluated. Two metrics, the mean absolute error (MAE) and symmetric mean absolute percentage error (SMAPE), are utilized to evaluate the forecasting models. MAE measures the error of the models by calculating the average absolute differences between the predicted and actual values. The formula for MAE is as follows:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (8)$$

In this formula, n represents the number of observations, y_i denotes the actual value, and \hat{y}_i represents the predicted value. MAE's advantage lies in its measurement being in data-native units, enabling easy interpretation and comparison of errors across different models. Additionally, SMAPE is another metric employed to evaluate the forecasting models. SMAPE computes the average percentage difference between predicted and actual values, considering the absolute difference in relation to the sum of predicted and actual values. Its formula is defined as follows:

$$SMAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{(|y_i| + |\hat{y}_i|)/2} \times 100 \quad (9)$$

SMAPE offers the advantage of expressing the error as a percentage, making it easier to interpret the accuracy of the models regardless of the scale or magnitude of the data being forecasted. By utilizing both MAE and SMAPE as evaluation metrics, the methods can be thoroughly assessed from different perspectives, considering both the absolute and relative errors. Both MAE and SMAPE are calculated as an average of prediction errors made for multiple charging sessions in the test dataset. However, the analysis of average error does not provide a full picture over the error distributions. To address this, we also include density plots of absolute error distributions. Furthermore, the assessment of computation times for model training and deployment is made using the same hardware setup – a 2020 M1 Macbook Pro.

5. Results and discussion

Tables 3 and 4 report measurements of mean absolute error (MAE) of predictions produced by models trained with datasets of different look-back periods. The percentage errors are detailed in the Tables 5 and 6. The visualization of the errors is given in Fig. 6.

In terms of prediction error, we observe that when compared to the benchmarks, most of the forecasting methods succeed in beating the user input estimations, marked with a dashed line in Fig. 6. The other benchmark, the historical average per user, generates predictions with a smaller error. To assess the influence of user registration, we evaluate the performance of the model with and without this input as part of the numerical feature vector. The LGBM and SimS configurations without user logs perform significantly worse. However, the results indicate that it is still possible to make predictions with higher accuracy than the estimates derived from user requests. Without user identification, both LGBM and SimS methods deliver more accurate predictions in terms of mean absolute error, however, the percentage error of the energy demand predictions is more inflated relative to the user predictions benchmark.

While the look-back period increases, the error of the historical mean increases in both energy and connection time estimations. This is expected behavior since over longer periods the distributions of the variable become more diverse, and taking the mean value does not incorporate the correlations between arrival time and the target variables. The fact that the historical mean of the same user benchmark hits the lowest error among all models when predicting the parking duration of EVs, particularly using the data of the last 60 days, indicates consistency in the data. This suggests a high regularity in peoples' behavior. This may be due to the fact that the data describe charging sessions of EVs in a workspace environment, where people tend to have a regular schedule. However, this is not true for the prediction of the energy demands, where the I-GMM and Logged Similar Sessions (L-SimS) models outperform the mean benchmark. For the percentage deviation, the data-driven models are consistently more accurate than mean benchmark. This suggest that the models succeed in capturing the proportional errors across different magnitudes of actual values.

It is observed that the prediction error generated with a gradient-boosted model generally decreases as the look-back period increases. The model is able to capture more of the underlying patterns and trends in the data as more historical data is incorporated into the model. This is a common observation with machine learning models. The LGBM algorithm may not be able to learn the underlying patterns in the data, as well as other algorithms designed for small datasets. The reason lies in the leaf structure of the decision trees that grow [22]. The other model designs, GMM and SimS, are less data intensive. The Gaussian mixture model is a probabilistic model that assumes that the data are generated from a mixture of Gaussian distributions. Therefore, GMMs can make use of a prior assumption about the Gaussian nature of the variable distribution to make better predictions in data-scarce environments. SimS shows stable error performance across different look-back periods. The method is most influenced by the most recent data points, as it searches a set of sessions most similar in terms of temporal features.

The quality of the predictions produced with GMM-based algorithms varies between the variables of energy demand and parking duration. For energy demand, the error is more consistent along all look-back periods. For the parking duration, the relationship is more ambiguous. When the look-back period of the training set increases, initially, the quality of the predictions is improving. However, the error starts rising for datasets that exceed 120 days in length. This occurrence is indicative of an existing trade-off within GMM models between model performance and data size, also observed in [4]. From the analysis of the time-series plots in Fig. 2 and the techniques used, it is hypothesized that the primary reason for the error swing is the inability of the models to adapt to "data drifts", defined as changes in statistical properties

Table 3
Mean Average Error [kWh] of energy delivery forecasts.

Look-back period	LGBM	SimS	Logged user				Benchmark	
			LGBM-L	SimS-L	P-GMM	I-GMM	Hist. Mean per user	User input
30	5.177	4.034	5.453	1.645	1.687	1.687	1.823	7.174
60	5.73	4.211	2.449	1.413	1.491	1.339	1.809	7.174
120	5.495	4.031	1.809	1.102	1.747	1.655	3.383	7.174
240	4.346	3.85	1.458	1.072	1.493	1.566	3.696	7.174
360	4.479	3.807	1.52	1.195	1.723	1.725	4.138	7.174
480	4.375	3.862	1.403	1.177	1.709	1.695	4.093	7.174

Table 4
Mean Average Error [h] of parking duration forecasts.

Look-back period	LGBM	SimS	Logged user				Benchmark	
			LGBM-L	SimS-L	P-GMM	I-GMM	Hist. Mean per user	User input
30	2.532	2.262	2.506	1.805	2.148	2.132	1.764	2.534
60	2.541	2.139	2.173	1.75	1.723	1.647	1.534	2.534
120	2.481	2.146	1.882	1.777	3.122	3.062	1.812	2.534
240	2.503	2.222	1.919	1.619	3.438	3.692	1.694	2.534
360	2.47	2.154	1.799	1.59	3.944	4.019	1.997	2.534
480	2.504	2.176	1.857	1.58	4.0	3.958	2.029	2.534

Table 5
Symmetric Mean Average Percentage Error of energy delivery forecasts.

Look-back period	LGBM	SimS	Logged user				Benchmark	
			LGBM-L	SimS-L	P-GMM	I-GMM	Hist. Mean per user	User input
30	33.05	28.75	33.46	12.45	14.89	14.97	12.85	27.93
60	33.4	28.66	16.59	10.41	13.72	12.56	13.68	27.93
120	33.76	27.77	13.58	7.7	15.81	15.04	15.75	27.93
240	30.91	27.56	11.08	7.88	14.44	15.05	16.69	27.93
360	31.4	27.17	11.56	8.08	15.39	15.71	17.19	27.93
480	30.91	27.53	11.04	7.97	15.59	15.79	17.27	27.93

Table 6
Symmetric Mean Average Percentage Error of parking duration forecasts.

Look-back period	LGBM	SimS	Logged user				Benchmark	
			LGBM-L	SimS-L	P-GMM	I-GMM	Hist. Mean per user	User input
30	17.35	15.84	17.35	13.13	15.3	17.74	15.44	23.06
60	17.81	15.09	14.93	12.78	12.76	12.51	14.07	23.06
120	17.25	15.05	12.86	12.62	15.02	14.97	16.98	23.06
240	17.39	15.67	13.1	11.5	15.92	17.52	16.32	23.06
360	17.15	15.39	12.32	11.04	16.31	17.15	17.7	23.06
480	17.36	15.57	12.5	10.93	18.2	16.79	18.19	23.06

of the parking duration time series. In other words, changes in data distribution over time can make it challenging for models trained on earlier data to perform well on later data, leading to increased errors. Considering the alternative algorithms, LGBM employs variance stabilization, while the SimS model is designed to select a sample of recent historical sessions.

We refer to the density plots of the absolute error distributions in Fig. 7 for a more complete analysis of the error distribution of the predictions. It can be observed that the user requests, marked in a dash line, generally show over-forecasting errors, while they underestimate the charging energy. It is also apparent that LGBM's predictions of parking duration exhibit a systemic bias towards under-forecasting, resulting in an asymmetrical error distribution. The Similar Sessions and I-GMM methods show a symmetric error distribution, centered at zero. The enlarged plots in 7(b) and 7(d) give a detailed view on the tails of the error distribution. The plot in 7(b) displays irregularities in the tails of error distributions, most pronounced for cluster-based I-GMM, but also present for LGBM and SimS predictions. This suggests potential weakness in capturing extreme values or outliers. Notably,

the perturbations are absent in the positive tail for LGBM and SimS, meaning that these models show no risk in extreme overestimation.

Our assessment of model performance also includes an evaluation of the computational speed taken in training and deployment of forecasting models. The results are displayed in Tables 7 and 8. SimS model is not included in the evaluation of training time, since the similarity scores are calculated at each instance the model is deployed. From the Table 7, it can be observed that the I-GMM model is significantly faster in terms of training time compared to the LGBM and P-GMM models. Although P-GMM and I-GMM employ the same principle, population-level GMM takes the extra step of tuning the weights of the Gaussian components based on individual user data. The weight-tuning step slows down the training of a P-GMM model, making it close to the training time of LGBM. The latter uses more time due to extra hyperparameter optimization. Small datasets are particularly susceptible to overfitting, and hyperparameter optimization can help mitigate this risk. Furthermore, as the look-back period increases, the training time for all models tends to increase as well, which is also expected, since more data is used for training. Once the model is

Fig. 6. Exploring the Impact of Varying Training Set Size on Mean Absolute Error Metrics for Model Predictions.

Fig. 7. Comparison of Parking Duration and Charging Energy Demand Predictions by Different Models: Absolute Error Distributions. The density plots are positioned at the top for Parking Duration and at the bottom for Charging Energy Demand. They are displayed at full scale on the left and zoomed in on the tails of the distributions on the right. The three models analyzed are I-GMM, LGBM, and a newly proposed similar sessions method. User-input requests' predictions are included for benchmarking purposes. The color groups are used to indicate the type of model. Different shades of the same color indicate variation in different look-back periods. Darker shades mark models trained in larger training sets with longer look-back periods.

Table 7
Training time [s] for varying model configurations and look-back periods.

Look-back period	LGBM	P-GMM	I-GMM
30	23.734	17.598	0.605
60	25.660	19.867	0.901
120	25.475	41.270	2.231
240	34.857	55.285	3.373
360	32.255	66.570	4.191
480	50.035	64.673	4.279

Table 8
Deployment time [ms] per univariate prediction of an EV charging session parameter for varying model configurations and look-back periods.

Look-back period	LGBM	IGMM	PGMM	SimS
30	0.010	0.179	0.185	0.889
60	0.021	0.178	0.180	0.802
120	0.011	0.161	0.170	0.834
240	0.021	0.162	0.159	0.937
360	0.010	0.180	0.164	1.009
480	0.008	0.152	0.157	1.031

trained on the available data, it can be used to make predictions about the behavior of the EV user using the user identification and the arrival time. This step, known as model deployment, involves applying the trained model to new, unseen data. Our results, presented in Table 8, demonstrate that LGBM requires significantly less execution time compared to GMM-based models and SimS, with a difference of up to an order of magnitude and two orders of magnitude respectively. LGBM models use decision trees to partition the feature space into regions, and the prediction is based on the majority response. Decision trees' inference can be calculated independently and largely parallelized. When deploying the GMM-based model, the probability density of observing a data point is calculated by summing over K components, representing the number of typical profiles in the data. This requires calculating the probability density for each component, which involves calculating the Mahalanobis distance between the data point and the mean of each component, as well as the determinant of the covariance matrix. Evidently, this process is more computationally expensive. Despite taking longer to deploy, the SimS model is capable of achieving a reasonable prediction time of approximately 1 ms per prediction. The extra time is required for the model to calculate cosine similarity metrics and identify the sessions that are most similar to a given session in the testing data. Note that SimS does not require prior training, which makes it more robust to data drift. Considering data scaling, LGBM, I-GMM and P-GMM models show no clear correlation between deployment time and the look-back period. SimS deployment time is more aligned with the size of the data. However, it remains within a feasible range since the frequency of the predictions is limited by the frequency of the arriving vehicles, while the historical data used in similarity calculations are sparse time-series data.

6. Conclusions

The study aims to evaluate the performance of four methods in forecasting the behavior of the EV user in terms of energy demand and parking duration. The models evaluated in the study are LGBM, P-GMM, I-GMM, and SimS. The study investigates the influence of the look-back period on model performance and the impact of the user predictor variable. The results show that data-driven models can provide predictions with better accuracy than the user input requests. Notably, LGBM and SimS models generally outperform the rest of the models. The historical mean per user benchmark hits the lowest error when predicting the connection time of EVs, while the I-GMM and SimS-L models outperform the mean benchmark when predicting energy demands. The quality of the predictions produced with GMM-based algorithms varies between the variables of energy demand and parking

duration. Although the error is less aligned with the size of the data, it is found that the error in the estimate of parking duration increased to a higher level with datasets exceeding 120 days in length. The study also evaluates the computational speed of training and deployment of forecasting models. The results show that the LGBM model requires significantly less execution time compared to the GMM-based models and SimS.

Overall, the study demonstrates the effectiveness of data-driven models in forecasting the behavior of EV users. The proposed SimS method provides a promising solution to predict the parameters of a charging session. By avoiding the usual limitations of traditional clustering techniques, we offer a robust and efficient approach that is tailored to the characteristics of the charging session data. The method shows superior accuracy under various data availability conditions. We show that potential concerns about slower computational performance are valid. However, the method remains feasible in applications dealing with forecasting sparse time-series data, such as those related to EV charging sessions.

For further research, it is worth investigating the synergies between elements within the optimal scheduling framework of the electric vehicle charging process pictured in Fig. 1(b). Particularly, the promising subject is integration of the SimS forecast into a smart charging optimization. The Similar Sessions method has the capacity to describe uncertainty by generating multiple scenarios drawn from similar sessions. Therefore, it becomes possible to account for potential randomness in the system and perform a stochastic optimization. Additionally, user arrival generation is a challenging problem in itself, as the subject time-series are irregular event-based, meaning it is binary, sparse, and non-equidistant. Specialized techniques are required to treat and model such data.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Evgenii Genov: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Cedric De Cauwer:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision. **Gilles Van Krieking:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Thierry Coosemans:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Maarten Messagie:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

I have shared the link to the repository, including the script for downloading the data.

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